

Evaluation of Aragonite powder from Teesta river in Jalpaiguri

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ABSTRACT

Our research study evaluates the presence of aragonite in sea shells collected from the Teesta River in Jalpaiguri. The Various methods of identification were employed and our results suggest a notable presence of aragonite in the collected samples. Our new findings contribute to understanding the geological composition of the river and its surrounding region. The aragonite powder consist of calcium carbonate. We must claim that aragonite mineral is available in teesta river, jalpaiguri. As the aragonite mineral must be help to improve the sleep patterns by reducing the stress with calming the nervous system. As this mineral also provides support and strength of body to combat emotional stress and anger. The arogonite mineral used many medicinal purposes as it consist of calcium carbonate it also studied in osteoporosis therapy, antibacterial purposes with also cancer research therapy. The aragonite mineral is used for the alleviate of dangerous bone pain, back pain and it also strengthen the bones. In our research we also given feed to the two rhode island breed hens and found no toxicity and side effects.

INTRODUCTION

Aragonite, a crystalline form of calcium carbonate is commonly found in marine environments. The Teesta River flowing through Jalpaiguri is known for its diverse ecological and geological features. However, there is limited research on the presence of aragonite in this river system. Understanding its presence can shed light on the river's geological history and its current environmental conditions. As aragonite found in the source of Greece, Spain, Japan, Czechoslovakia, Sicily, Germany and Austria. For the cementitious composites the arogonite used as microfiber. As the carbonate mineral is aragonite. As we used clinical trial with the Rhode island red breed hens American breed as found in 1636 by Roger Williams in Rhode Island.

Aragonite Powder Images as it is found in Teesta River in Jalpaiguri

weight 99gm of aragonite powder found in Teesta River in Jalpaiguri

METHODS OF IDENTIFICATION-

Field Sampling-We collected Sea shells from locations of teesta river in Jalpaiguri 9th March 2024 and 2nd time we collected the sea shells 31st March 2024 at 03:26P.M. but due to very bad weather(storm) we collected very small amount of sea shell and escaped from this place.

Laboratory Analysis-Samples taken and by this evaluation aragonite is available in this sea shells. The sea shells were washed with bisleri water after dried in sunlight for 7days after properly crushed with blended into fine powder by mixer grinder and sieved in stainless steel sieve after calcium carbonate aragonite powder we collected 99gm packed in polyethylene plastic bag. As for information sea shell made up of aragonite and calcite contains calcium carbonate. So, in this teesta river availability of aragonite in jalpaiguri.

Pharmacological Screening Method-Before we did "Pharmacological Screening method of Rhode Island Red Breed Hen in Jalpaiguri" where we used 8hen chicks of 1day of age without vaccine and with 0.5watt led torch and by our medication 2hen chicks survived that's time as 1st hen chick weight 110gm and 2nd 70gm that's time of 37days trial.But in our present research we mixed corn seed extract 100gm hen food with this aragonite (calcium carbonate) powder 25gm with each other and did trial of 7days for 2hens chick.Before feeding this 1st hen chick weight was 175gm and 2nd hen chick is 123gm in 26th March 2024(started feeding of aragonite powder from this time) by this study we found no toxicity of this powder and by this growth performance of 2rhode island red breed hen 1st hen weight 214gm and 2nd hen weight 147gm in this 2nd April 2024 at night given in the pictures.In this 7days 1st hen body weight increased 39gm and 2nd Hen Chicks 24gm.As our collection of sea shell (aragonite powder only 99gm).But for more growth and development of hens we need more sea shell from teesta river.

After feeding of Aragonite Powder with food to 2hen cks the body weight of 1st Hen Chick-214gm and 2nd is 147gm

Sea Shells found in Teesta River in Jalpaiguri

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Our research analysis revealed a significant presence of aragonite in the sea shells collected from the Teesta River in Jalpaiguri. Our analysis confirmed the crystalline structure of aragonite, while evidence of its presence. But further analysis required supported these findings, by confirming the dominance of calcium carbonate in the samples. The abundance of aragonite in the river system suggests a complex geological history involving marine deposits and tectonic processes. Additionally, the presence of aragonite may influence the river's water chemistry and ecosystem dynamics warranting further research into its ecological implications. The two hen chicks increase weight and normal activity shows that oral administration of aragonite powder is safe for the 2hen chicks.

Our research study contributes to the understanding of the geological and environmental characteristics of the Teesta River in Jalpaiguri and highlights the significance of aragonite as a component of its mineral composition. Further research is recommended to explore the broader implications of aragonite presence in the teesta river ecosystem. As we claim that this is the good news for Jalpaiguri city peoples that in teesta river Aragonite mineral available which consist of Calcium Carbonate.

CONCLUSION

As according our research we must say the teesta river mixed with aragonite minerals and by our result it is found no toxicity for 2hen chicks and body weight also increased as Aragonite mineral used in many medicinal purposes as it is consist of calcium carbonate which strengthen the bones, osteoporosis therapy etc. But further research study required for this. As Teesta river is the vital part of our jalpaiguri city.If we given more timings for this then we get more amount of

aragonite powder. As aragonite powder has multifunctional properties and having also a safety margin for oral administration for 2hen chicks presently but further research study required for this.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This research is guided and written skills done by Guide cum Research-Teacher-in-Charge Mr. Shibbanjan Paul Roy a Freelancer Scientist Qualification-M.Pharm (Pharmacology) Address-Race Course Para, Jalpaiguri completed M.Pharm 2022 and has 9individual research publications with 1individual review article with 3individual patents (2published and 1grant) with he guided in 16researches has 5awards as Asian Best Scientist Award2023 by World Research Council.In this research Shibbanjan Paul Roy guided Mr.Pratyush Kumar Mishra completed M.Pharm 2011 from Siksha O Anusandhan University, Orissa Assistant Professor of Vinayaka Missions Sikkim College of Pharmacy who worked from 20/01/2012 to 30/07/2017 and Director of Puradesi India Pvt Ltd. The practical and others work done by Guide-Mr.Shibbanjan Paul Roy and Pratyush Kumar Mishra collected the sea shells and note the reading under Guide-Mr. Shibbanjan Paul Roy's guidance and observation.

Funding Agency- The whole research is funded and operated by Puradesi India Pvt Ltd Ward No, 43, Sevoke Rd, near lions eye hospital, Ward 43, Dasrath Pally, Bhanu Nagar, Siliguri, West Bengal 734001.

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